

8T – SUSY and W Duality

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Abstract:

By analyzing the W duality among the boson of the weak interaction and the electron it is possible to correlate The SEW unification of the 8T thesis to SUSY. Since the three coupling terms are aligned on the same net variation element, which is identical to the electron, it is possible to present the following morphisms, from a photon to the electron, and from a Gluon to the electron.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the first coupling term in the primorial:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + (e)] + W^-$$

The electron and the Boson of the weak interaction are represented by the same element, the majestic three is for the electron, and the three net variations are for the W^+ boson. The kernel is the three and the image is both the electron and the W^+ Boson. Such a duality among those two is in agreement with modern particle physics that states that the electron and the W^+ Bosons have the same charge. The same applies to the opposite charges. Because of the duality of those two.

Because there is no numerical difference, we can replace the order as mentioned in the 8T thesis, page seventy-eight.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + W^-] + (e)$$

We can also replace the actual elements:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + W^-] + W^-$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + (e)] + (e)$$

The coupling term with two electrons as an example, could describe the motion of free electron that could join another atom, the electron tradeoff that ignite the entire chemistry. In addition, we can make a prediction regarding photon emission. In particular, the author predict that photon can be emitted from the Boson of the weak interaction. Therefore, in a way we have Bosons emitting Bosons. The emission is described by the third coupling term, given by the equivalence relation among the electron and W^- Boson, i.e., W duality:

$$W^- \equiv (e) \tag{1.61}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \equiv [(24 * 5) + (W^-)] + \gamma$$

Since the coupling constants series is commutative, we can go further and make an additional prediction:

$$[(24 * 5) + (W^-)] + \gamma \longrightarrow [(24 * 5) + \gamma] + W^-$$

In the 8T thesis, page twenty-nine we have presented the SEW unification by aligning the net variation element of the three couplings. That was by an exchange of two net variations from the third to the first coupling term, so all three would be at $N_V = +3$. The key point in the context of SUSY is the following, since there exist the W duality, the morphisms presented in SEW unification applies to the electron.

$$8 + (1) + 2: [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 * 5) + (3)] + \mathbf{3}$$

$$8 + (1) + 2 \rightarrow 8 + (3)$$

The two real exchanges between the third and the first will modify the same middle element the exact same manner as presented in the 8T thesis. The only term we can vary is the left, as we want to ensure duality among the forces; we cannot touch the net variation, marked in black;

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + \mathbf{3}.$$

We cannot vary the invariant three; the modification will be to the left term in the coupling series;

$$(8 * 3) + 2 = 26$$

The restrictions imposed on such variation on the strong are the same as presented in the thesis. I.e. it must be to an infinitesimal interval. The physical meaning of such equivalence relation in high energy is a morphism between the Bosons. A gluon morphism the weak interaction W^+, W^-, Z Bosons, and photon morphism to the W^+, W^-, Z Bosons.

$$\gamma \rightarrow W^+ / W^- / Z$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + W^+$$

$$[8 + (g + 2)] \rightarrow 8 + W^+ / W^- / Z$$

(1) At high energies there exist a morphism among the photon and the Gluon to the Bosons of the weak interaction. The Gluon at high energy can become a longer-range mediator (assuming we consider weak as longer ranged).

Now take the duality relation manifested in the term:

$$W^- \equiv (e) \quad (1.61)$$

And the new morphisms would be:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &\rightarrow e^- \\ [8 + (g + 2)] &\rightarrow 8 + e^- \end{aligned}$$

An extension on the main prediction:

(1.1) Because of the Duality (1.61), at high energies there exist a morphism between The Bosons of the first and third interaction into matter. A photon into an Electron, and a Gluon into an Electron.

This version of SUSY does not include the Super partners of all particles but rather a morphism between particles we already know exist. The entire idea of SUSY is contained in the Primordial coupling series in the first and second representations.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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